

All-Spiking ECG Analysis for Arrhythmia Classification on Low-Power FPGA

Matteo Antonio Scrugli, Gianluca Leone, Paola Busia, Luigi Raffo, *Fellow, IEEE*, and Paolo Meloni, *Fellow, IEEE*

Abstract—Accurate and energy-efficient classification of cardiac arrhythmias is essential for real-time electrocardiogram (ECG) monitoring in wearable healthcare systems. This work introduces an end-to-end, spike-driven approach for ECG analysis, in which Spiking Neural Network (SNN) address arrhythmia detection on an event-based input. The signal encoding employs delta modulation on the raw ECG waveform as well as its first and second derivatives, capturing richer temporal and morphological features and enhancing classification performance compared to baseline approaches. Heartbeats are classified into five categories, as defined by the AAMI standard, achieving 98.4% accuracy on the MIT-BIH Arrhythmia Database. Unlike traditional methods, our approach removes the need for separate filtering, segmentation, or peak detection algorithms, relying instead on a unified, event-driven architecture. To support this enhanced processing methodology, we have implemented an optimized hardware architecture based on a low-power Lattice iCE40-UltraPlus FPGA. This design eliminates redundant computations by unifying peak detection and classification within the same processing pipeline, reducing power consumption while maintaining low inference times. Performance evaluations indicate an execution time of just 4.05 ms per classification, with energy usage optimized to 36.86 μJ , substantially outperforming existing FPGA-based solutions.

Index Terms—Spiking neural networks, real-time monitoring, healthcare

I. INTRODUCTION

Cardiovascular diseases remain a leading cause of mortality worldwide, making real-time cardiac monitoring a critical need in modern healthcare. Early detection of arrhythmias, irregularities in the heartbeat that may signal severe underlying conditions, requires continuous, high-fidelity monitoring [1]. The electrocardiogram (ECG) is the primary diagnostic tool for this purpose, yet its real-time analysis on wearable platforms is hampered by strict computational and power

constraints.

Accurate segmentation and detection of the QRS complex are fundamental steps in ECG analysis, as they enable heart rate estimation, arrhythmia classification, and other critical diagnostic tasks. Traditional ECG processing methods employ filtering and thresholding mechanisms to detect QRS complexes. Although effective, these techniques typically require dedicated hardware to manage variations in noise, heart rate, and signal morphology, thus limiting the system flexibility or in some cases even their applicability in low-power wearable devices.

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Matteo A. Scrugli, Gianluca Leone, Paola Busia, Luigi Raffo and Paolo Meloni are with the DIEE, University of Cagliari, Cagliari, Italy (e-mail: matteo.a.scrugli@unica.it, gianluca.leone94@unica.it, paola.busia@unica.it, raffo@unica.it, paolo.meloni@unica.it).

An efficient alternative to traditional ECG processing lies in event-based methodologies, which operate by responding only to significant changes in the signal rather than continuously processing every data point. Event-driven approaches are particularly well-suited for physiological signals like ECG, which are inherently sparse and characterized by transient, high-information features such as QRS complexes. In this context, Spiking Neural Networks (SNNs) provide a promising, biologically inspired event-based solution to leverage the sparse and transient nature of ECG signals, operating only when significant changes occur. In our approach, the continuous ECG waveform is converted into discrete spike trains via a delta modulation strategy that encodes both first and second-

order derivatives.

To fully exploit the advantages of SNNs, our system is deployed on the open-source SYNTzulu platform [2], targeting a Lattice iCE40-UltraPlus Field Programmable Gate Array (FPGA). FPGAs offer a highly configurable hardware architecture where Digital Signal Processor (DSP) slices accelerate operations such as addition, multiplication, and multiply-accumulate functions; flexible Block Random Access Memory (BRAM) efficiently stores on-chip SNN models and activation data; and programmable logic (PL) provides the adaptability required for rapid algorithm evolution.

This work introduces a unified SNN-based architecture for real-time ECG analysis, combining peak detection and arrhythmia classification within a single processing pipeline. By leveraging event-driven computation and spike-based encoding, the system removes the need for conventional filtering stages, reducing computational cost and improving efficiency. Delta modulation on signal derivatives enhances the classification accuracy, while hardware optimizations ensure low-latency, low-power execution on FPGA platforms.

To summarize, this work presents an SNN-based classification system for arrhythmia detection that attains an accuracy comparable to the state of the art in SNN research, introducing the following main contributions:

- We develop an advanced encoding method using delta modulation on the ECG signal and its first and second derivatives, thereby enhancing sparsity and preserving essential morphological features.
- We introduce an event-driven peak detection mechanism that efficiently identifies QRS complexes without relying on traditional filtering and thresholding techniques, reducing computational complexity and improving adaptability to signal variations.
- We improve the state of the art of existing FPGA solutions, demonstrating an optimized ultra-low power processing unit implementation on the Lattice iCE40-UltraPlus FPGA, enabling real-time classification within 4.05 ms and with 36.86 μJ energy consumption.

Figure 1 shows the architecture of the proposed system, which performs ECG analysis by combining spike-based peak detection and classification. The input signal is first encoded via delta modulation applied to the raw waveform and its first and second derivatives. The encoded traces are processed on-chip by an SNN module dedicated to QRS complex detection. Upon detection of a peak, a second SNN module is triggered to perform arrhythmia classification, avoiding unnecessary computation during non-relevant signal segments.

Compared with our earlier prototype [3], which relied on an external Pan-Tompkins front-end, the present design collapses both R-peak detection and arrhythmia classification into a single, fully event-driven SNN pipeline. This integration not only eliminates redundant pre-processing and inter-module transfers but also reuses the same leaky-integrate-and-fire (LIF) cores, spike routers, and weight-memory layout, thereby reducing logic utilization and static power. Furthermore, the FPGA implementation now supports 8-bit quantization-aware training and concurrent execution of two SNNs through a lightweight context switch. Beyond architectural optimizations, we extend

the experimental evaluation by (i) systematically testing robustness under noise using the MIT-BIH Noise Stress Test Database, and (ii) applying the standard Chazal partition [4] to assess inter-patient generalization, and (iii) training and evaluating the model from scratch on the MIT-BIH Atrial Fibrillation Database to verify applicability across heterogeneous clinical scenarios. These methodological and hardware-level advances make the present contribution substantially broader and deeper than the previous conference version.

The paper is structured as follows. In Section II, we review the literature on SNN-based ECG classification. Section III details the proposed approach, including dataset selection, spike-based peak detection, and encoding. Section IV describes the FPGA implementation, focusing on the integrated SNN pipeline. Experimental results, including SNNs accuracy, power efficiency, and performance analysis, are presented in Section V. Finally, conclusions and future directions are discussed in Section VI.

II. RELATED WORK

It is well established that wearable solutions play a crucial role in continuously monitoring chronic conditions while easing the burden on clinicians and hospital infrastructures [1]. Flexible, low-cost sensor technologies are increasingly available, such as textile-based ECG monitors [5] or wristbands, smartwatches, wearable vests, skin patches, and implantable devices, which rely on diverse biomarkers [6].

Simultaneously, deep learning has significantly advanced ECG analysis, enabling arrhythmia classification with accuracies often exceeding 98–99% on standard benchmarks [7]–[13], either with conventional CNN-based approaches [8], [13], or with latest generation large-scale models such as transformers [10], [11]. However, the complexity and computational demands of these solutions limit their direct deployment on wearable devices, leading to the introduction of lightweight CNN architectures [9], [12] that, while more efficient, sometimes struggle to match the diagnostic precision of their larger counterparts.

Motivated by the need to reconcile high diagnostic accuracy with the efficiency required for wearable, real-time applications, our work explores an event-driven SNN approach. This method leverages the sparse, temporal dynamics of ECG signals to deliver efficient, low-power arrhythmia classification without sacrificing performance. Recent advances in ECG classification utilizing SNNs have set new benchmarks in accuracy and efficiency.

Lightweight SNN architectures targeting real-time arrhythmia detection and balancing accuracy and computational cost, for optimized execution on specialized ASIC-based solutions, are introduced in [14]–[22]. Notably, the study in [15] introduced an ultra-low-power processor tailored for wearable devices, by transforming an Artificial Neural Network (ANN) into an SNN-based model, whereas the system introduced in [14], [19] leverages an SNN trained through spatio-temporal backpropagation. A distinguishing feature of the models in [17], [18] is their capability to handle inter-patient classification, a challenging task requiring robust generalization across unseen patient data. Furthermore, [19] presents

Fig. 1: Overview of the proposed ECG monitoring system. The ECG signal is encoded into spike trains through delta modulation applied to the raw signal, its first derivative, and second derivative. A dedicated SNN based on Leaky Integrate-and-Fire neurons detects QRS complexes in the encoded signal. Classification is performed only when a peak is detected, using a second LIF-based SNN to assign the heartbeat to one of the five arrhythmia classes: N, S, V, F, or Q.

an SNN classifier that exploits quantization-aware training and robustness-oriented optimisations, while [16] extends this paradigm by introducing a time-domain SNN processor for ECG classification, featuring a memory-delay-line architecture and event-driven wave generation to minimise power and area overheads. These works demonstrate an exceptional energy efficiency, resulting from the targeted ASIC implementations.

Our work aims at enhancing the flexibility of ASIC-based solutions, leveraging reconfigurable FPGA implementations. Compared to existing alternatives from the state of the art, targeting multiple high-end FPGAs to implement complex neural models for the accurate emulation of neural activity and learning processes, such as [23]–[26], in this work, we focus on a lightweight design suitable to fit the hardware resources and power budget of the wearable domain. Relevant references in the literature are represented by [27] and [28], exploring alternative FPGA-based architectures for the implementation of a specialized SNN integrating an attention mechanism, and a binarized SNN designed to minimize computational load and hardware complexity, offering an efficient alternative for resource-constrained environments. These works provide a reference for the power efficiency of currently available FPGA-based solutions, which we aim to improve in order to reduce the gap compared to ASIC-based solutions.

Furthermore, many of these solutions focus on the power efficiency of event-driven classification, relying on specialized SNN accelerators. However, real-time ECG analysis demands more than classification, as accurate R-peak detection is essential for effective signal segmentation. The system described in [15] incorporates an FPGA to facilitate data handling, whereas the methodologies in [14], [19], and [21] implement LC-ADC encoding separately on an auxiliary FPGA. Notably, peak detection remains unaddressed in [17] and [18].

Our work builds upon these advancements by integrating peak detection, signal encoding, and SNN-based classification within an FPGA-driven, low-power design. This approach maximizes efficiency by consolidating all essential processing steps into a single device.

There are several approaches for detecting the R-peak or the

QRS complex in ECG signals, each with specific characteristics and requirements. Some methods are based on advanced algorithms, such as wavelet transforms [29] or artificial neural networks [30]–[32], which provide high accuracy but require intensive processing by DSPs or CPUs, making them unsuitable for wearable devices due to high power consumption. Other approaches take advantage of low computational cost techniques, such as on-chip cross-correlation [33], integrated-and-fire automata [34] or pulse-based triggering methods [35], which allow real-time processing with simplified hardware.

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An alternative to conventional signal processing techniques for QRS complex detection is represented by event-based approaches. Event-based representations trigger system responses only upon significant signal variations, reducing redundant computations and enabling low-latency inference. In this context, delta modulation is particularly effective, converting continuous ECG signals into discrete spike trains by encoding the temporal evolution of the signal and its derivatives into binary event sequences. The study in [36] introduces an event-driven SoC that labels each detected QRS complex and maps every label to a dedicated spike class, enabling in-sensor processing with negligible energy overhead. Prior works, such as [37], have shown how parallel Delta modulators can effectively delineate ECG signals through Local Maximum and Minimum Point strategies, exceeding 99% in both Positive Predictive Value (PPV) and True Positive Rate (TPR). Similarly, [38] employed a second-order ternary Delta modulator to capture slope variations, also surpassing

99% in the same metrics while reducing baseline drift. Although these methods underscore the benefits of event-based encoding, they frequently depend on specialized ASICs or external accelerators, which can limit design flexibility. In our work, we adapt these insights into a fully integrated FPGA-based approach, incorporating peak detection within the main processing pipeline.

Due to the wide spectral bandwidth of ECG signals, oversampling is typically employed to mitigate distortion from anti-aliasing filters and to ensure high-fidelity encoding [37], [39]. However, this increases the sampling rate and data volume. In contrast, our encoding strategy avoids oversampling by generating a spike-based representation that preserves essential signal features without increasing data rate, maintaining temporal precision and computational efficiency.

As a key contribution, we propose a fully FPGA-based peak detection system embedding the entire processing pipeline within FPGA logic, eliminating external computation. By leveraging existing delta modulation hardware, we efficiently encode ECG signals and reuse modulator blocks to reduce complexity and power consumption. Unlike conventional approaches requiring extensive filtering, our event-driven method directly extracts QRS features from spike-based encoding, minimizing data overhead and computational load. Additionally, we enhance the encoding by applying delta modulation to the first and second ECG derivatives, refining feature extraction, improving classification accuracy, and maintaining superior energy efficiency compared to existing FPGA-based solutions.

III. METHOD

In this section, we detail our proposed system by introducing the reference dataset, outlining the spike-generation encoding scheme, describing the chosen SNN topology, and presenting the FPGA-based processor utilized.

A. Dataset

This study employs the MIT-BIH Arrhythmia Database [40], [41], an extensively annotated dataset containing 48 half-hour ECG recordings gathered from ambulatory patients by the BIH Arrhythmia Laboratory. This dataset encompasses a wide range of normal and pathological cardiac rhythms, serving as a valuable benchmark for ECG-based algorithm development and evaluation.

Each recording is originally captured using a two-channel configuration and sampled at 360 Hz. Given the impact of electrode placement on signal integrity, our analysis is standardized to a single-channel approach, specifically utilizing the Modified Limb Lead II (MLLII), which is consistently available across all subjects.

In line with established research [9]–[11], [42], for the only steps inherent in the classifier, we exclude ECG recordings containing paced beats, namely records “102”, “104”, “107”, and “217”. Additionally, following the AAMI standard [43], we classify heartbeats into five key categories essential for arrhythmia detection: N (normal beats), S (supraventricular ectopic beats), V (ventricular ectopic beats), F (fusion beats),

and Q (unclassifiable beats). This categorization aligns with clinical standards, ensuring precise and clinically relevant arrhythmia classification.

To investigate robustness to real-world signal artifacts, we extended the dataset by combining the MIT-BIH Arrhythmia Database with the MIT-BIH Noise Stress Test Database. Among the three available types of noise (baseline wander, muscle artifact, and electrode motion artifact), we selected the latter as the most challenging, due to its tendency to mimic ectopic beats and its resistance to simple filtering. Electrode motion artifacts were injected at SNR levels of 3 dB, 10 dB, and 24 dB, generating noise-augmented training and test sets.

In addition to the MIT-BIH Arrhythmia Database, we also considered the MIT-BIH Atrial Fibrillation Database. This dataset consists of 10-hour ECG recordings, sampled at 250 Hz with 12-bit resolution, and includes rhythm annotations for atrial fibrillation, atrial flutter, junctional rhythms, and normal beats.

B. Encoding method

In SNN-based classification, the continuous ECG signal must first be transformed into spike sequences. Our approach employs delta modulation, a well-established technique in signal processing and telecommunications, to digitize the analog signal while preserving critical information about its variations.

Delta encoding can be regarded as a general-purpose feature extraction mechanism. By reacting only to significant variations, it transforms the ECG into sparse event streams where amplitude transitions, slopes, and curvature changes become more explicit. This process does not directly identify individual fiducial points (Q, R, S), but rather emphasizes the temporal and morphological dynamics of the waveform. When applied not only to the raw signal but also to its first and second derivatives, the encoding provides complementary descriptors: the raw signal preserves overall morphology, the first derivative emphasizes gradients, and the second derivative captures curvature dynamics. This multi-level representation enriches the signal description and facilitates subsequent processing by SNNs.

Delta modulation outputs two spike trains, indicating positive and negative deviations relative to a predefined threshold δ . This threshold controls the spike density: lower values lead to densely packed spikes, capturing more detailed variations in the signal, while higher values produce sparser distributions, improving efficiency but potentially discarding finer details of the signal’s dynamics. A visualization of the encoding process, illustrated in Figure 2, focuses on a signal window centered around the QRS complex, specifically the R-peak of a normal heartbeat. Overlaid on the original ECG waveform, we present six spike traces: the topmost pair corresponds to the raw signal’s delta-modulated positive and negative variations, the middle pair represents the first derivative, and the bottom pair reflects the second derivative.

All signals undergo normalization within the range [0, 1], based on their respective extrema in the training dataset. Following extensive testing, we determined optimal threshold

Fig. 2: Illustration of a signal window centered on the beat of a non-arrhythmic heartbeat with the six signals generated through delta modulation overlaid.

values: $\delta = 0.003$ for the original ECG signal and $\delta = 0.006$ for both derivative signals. The encoding process is detailed in Algorithm 1, which systematically converts the ECG signal into spike trains using delta modulation principles.

Algorithm 1: ECG Encoding with Delta Modulation

Input: Normalized ECG signal
Result: Two signals of spikes, POS and NEG.

- 1 δ = First normalized ECG sample;
- 2 δ = δ ;
- 3 **while** Normalized ECG signal **do**
- 4 ECG sample;
- 5 **if** ECG sample $>$ δ + δ **then**
- 6 δ = ECG sample;
- 7 POS.append(spike);
- 8 **else**
- 9 POS.append(no-spike);
- 10 **if** ECG sample $<$ δ - δ **then**
- 11 δ = ECG sample;
- 12 NEG.append(spike);
- 13 **else**
- 14 NEG.append(no-spike);

C. SNN topology and training

The architecture of our spiking neural network is composed of sequential dense layers, as detailed in Table I. For its implementation, we employed SpikingJelly [44] for the peak detection task, while SLAYER [45] was used for arrhythmia classification. Both are high-level frameworks designed for managing SNNs, particularly suited for defining custom spiking neurons and synaptic behaviors. Both models adopt Leaky Integrate and Fire (LIF) neurons as their core computational units. In the case of SLAYER, the neuron model is based on Loihi’s Current-Based Leaky Integrate and Fire (CUBA LIF) [46], with a minor modification to simplify it into a standard LIF model to meet the constraints of our hardware platform.

As described in Equations 1, 2, and 3, each neuron processes incoming spikes s_{in} , which are weighted by synaptic parameters w , contributing to the neuron’s membrane potential v . In general, the membrane potential dynamics can be related to a temporal decay mechanism controlled by a decay factor α , as expressed in Equation 1. Specifically, the reset mechanism described in Equation 2 is implemented by *SpikingJelly*, where the threshold value is subtracted from the membrane potential upon crossing. Instead, in *SLAYER*, the membrane potential

TABLE I: Topology of the proposed SNN.

Layer	Synapse	Neuron
Dense Layer 1	6	64
Dense Layer 2	64	128
Dense Layer 3	128	64
Dense Layer 4	64	2 or 5

of each neuron is reset to zero whenever the threshold is exceeded, as described in Equation 3.

$$v'(t) = \alpha \cdot v(t) + \sum w \cdot s_{in}(t) \quad (1)$$

$$v(t+1) = \begin{cases} v'(t), & \text{if } v'(t) < \theta \\ v'(t) - \theta, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

$$v(t+1) = \begin{cases} v'(t), & \text{if } v'(t) < \theta \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

As shown in Equation 4, the neuron emits an output spike $s_{out}(t)$ when its voltage exceeds a certain threshold θ . The output spike can be represented as:

$$s_{out}(t+1) = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } v'(t) > \theta \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

The *axonal delay* defines the propagation time of spikes between neurons, introducing temporal dynamics in the network. For the peak detection model implemented with *SpikingJelly*, axonal delays were not used, as the framework does not support this feature. Conversely, in the arrhythmia classification model implemented with *SLAYER*, axonal delays were enabled on the first three layers, with a maximum delay set to 62 timesteps, to improve the network’s ability to capture temporal dependencies.

For both models, training was conducted on the Google Colab platform using T4 GPUs and the Adam optimizer with an initial learning rate of 0.001. After a patience of 20 epochs evaluated based on the validation loss, the learning rate was reduced by a factor of 10, until the early stop condition was met with a final learning rate of 0.00001. The batch size was fixed at 32 for all experiments.

Training is fully supervised and gradient-based, synaptic weights w are optimized in both models. In the *SLAYER*-based classifier, a limited set of neuronal parameters (firing threshold and decay constants) is also trainable, while the peak detection network implemented in *SpikingJelly* employs fixed

neuronal dynamics. Loss computation was performed using the *slayer.loss* module, adopting the *SpikeRate* loss function. This loss operates on the average output firing rate of each class neuron over the observation window, driving the target class toward a desired spike rate of 0.2 while suppressing non-target classes toward a lower rate of 0.03. As for other hyperparameters, the low and high spike rate settings were treated as hyperparameters and selected through a standard exploration on the validation set. This formulation enables rate-based discrimination and directly matches the spike-rate decoding strategy used during inference.

D. SNN for peak detection

Following the delta encoding process described in Section III-B, the binary spike trains derived from the original ECG signal are processed to detect ECG peaks, which are essential for accurate segmentation. Our approach utilizes the same SNN architecture for both peak detection and classification, optimizing hardware efficiency while maintaining distinct processing for each task.

The system encodes the first and second derivatives of the ECG signal using delta modulation, converting them into discrete spike representations. These spike trains serve as input to the peak detection SNN, which identifies peak locations by analyzing spike density variations.

The SNN architecture used for peak detection closely resembles the one employed for classification, with a key distinction in the number of output features. In this case, the network comprises two output classes: *beat* and *non-beat*, providing the information necessary for R peak detection.

To generate appropriate labels for training, the original annotations from the MIT-BIH Arrhythmia Database were reformulated. All heartbeat classes from MIT-BIH were grouped under the *beat* category, while a new *BASE* class was introduced to represent non-beat regions. This adjustment ensured a structured labeling approach, assigning a classification to every sample for training consistency. Since the original dataset provides labels only at peak locations, the *BASE* class was added to cover non-peak areas, enabling a continuous annotation scheme. Additionally, each MIT-BIH annotation was expanded by 45 samples on both sides, extending the temporal window around detected peaks.

For dataset partitioning, recordings were split into *train* (70%), *validation* (15%), and *test* (15%) sets. Data segments were extracted contiguously from each patient, maintaining the natural flow of the ECG signal. This methodology ensured that test data preserved temporal coherence, allowing continuous spike-based outputs during inference. Cross-validation was not performed for this task, and model selection relied on the held-out validation set.

During training, the ECG signal was segmented into overlapping windows of 90 samples, with a stride of 20 samples between consecutive windows. Each segmented window was assigned the label that appeared most frequently within it. However, to ensure robust labeling, a threshold was applied, the majority label had to constitute at least 80% of the samples within the window. If no label met this criterion, the

window was discarded to prevent ambiguous training data that could negatively impact model convergence. The final training set includes approximately 495 000 *non-beat* windows and 134 000 *beat* windows, resulting in a moderate class ratio of about four to one in favor of non-beat segments. Such a degree of imbalance remains slight and does not introduce significant bias into the training process.

During the training process, the SNN was optimized to generate a high spike rate for the *beat* class when a heartbeat was present in the segmented window while maintaining a low spike rate for the *non-beat* class. Conversely, when no heartbeat was detected in the window, the network was trained to generate a high spike rate for the *non-beat* class and a low rate for the *beat* class.

During the test phase, the input signal is processed continuously by the SNN (without pre-segmentation) to enable real-time operation. The model integrates two output neurons, one for each target class, and the class label at each time step is assigned by comparing the firing rates of the two neurons accumulated over a sliding temporal window, whose length is set to half of the training window.

To obtain discrete beat events from the resulting time-resolved class labels, consecutive samples assigned to the same class are grouped into contiguous intervals. For each interval classified as *beat*, a single beat event is generated and assigned to the temporal center of the interval, whereas intervals classified as *non-beat* are discarded.

E. SNN for peak classification

Data partitioning followed an intra-patient approach, wherein the dataset was split into 70% for training, 10% for validation, and 20% for testing. Unlike peak detection, which operates on dense sample-level annotations, peak classification is performed on beat-centered windows, where arrhythmic events, especially minority classes, are intrinsically sparse. For this reason, a larger fraction of data was allocated to the test set to improve the statistical reliability of the reported performance metrics, while the validation split was reduced to the minimum required for early stopping and model selection. Cross-validation was not performed for this task; instead, generalization was further assessed through a strict inter-patient evaluation using the standard Chazal partitioning protocol [4].

Notably, 89.5% of the heartbeats belong to class *N*, while classes *S*, *V*, *F*, and *Q* represent 2.8%, 7%, 0.8%, and a marginal fraction, respectively. To counteract this imbalance, we applied data augmentation techniques focused on minority classes, incorporating window shifts centered around the heartbeat peaks. Furthermore, the output of the SNN classifier is interpreted by analyzing the spike rate within a dedicated output window to determine the winning class.

IV. FPGA DEPLOYMENT

To execute the designed algorithm on an affordable and easily accessible device while leveraging the advantages of event-based processing, we deployed it on SYNTzulu, an open-source SNN processor previously adopted for other biosignals [2], [47]–[49]. The repository is publicly available at [50].

SYNtzu, shown in Figure 3, is based on a SoC template that integrates:

- a RISC-V processor for general supervision tasks and housekeeping, namely an instance of the SERV [51] microarchitecture, chosen for its resource-efficiency. Its duties include managing the input-output peripherals, overseeing the ECG signal acquisition through the SPI interface based on the desired sampling frequency, and transferring the output classification through the UART interface. It also handles the system initialization and the stand-by.
- two design-time configurable slots, called *encoding* and *decoding slots*, demanded to implement the conversion of input sample values into spikes and, viceversa, of output spikes into a usable result. The former implements the delta modulation algorithm as described in Section III-B. The latter implements the peak detection algorithm and the voting strategy as seen in Section III-D and III-E respectively.
- an SNN accelerator module, designed to operate on event-based temporal encoding while maintaining a clock-driven execution scheme. It receives input spikes from the encoding module and executes SNN inference in real time. The processor integrates two *neuron* modules, which share the workload by executing half of the neurons of each layer. Each neuron module is capable of accumulating four 8-bit synaptic weights per cycle to compute the synaptic current and to emulate Leaky Integrate-and-Fire dynamics, updating membrane potentials, and generating output spikes. Each neuron module is connected to a dedicated weight memory, initialized at boot with the network’s trained synaptic weights, and a spike memory, which stores intermediate results in the form of spikes. To enable event-driven processing, an *address generator* module dynamically fetches weights of active synapses, limiting memory accesses, and speeding up synaptic current computation. This mechanism improves energy efficiency by extending system standby periods. The output spikes are then passed to the decoding slot module.

We customized SYNtzu to support the ECG analysis algorithm at hand.

First, we modified the encoding slot. It includes a delta-encoding module, shared and employed consistently for spike generation for both peak detection and arrhythmia classification tasks. Encoded spikes are continuously routed to the accelerator, to be processed for peak detection. Moreover, to prepare spike train segments corresponding to peaks, a segmentation buffer continuously stores delta-encoded spikes. In this way, when the dedicated SNN detects a peak, a window of samples centered around the actual detection can be created and processed by the classification SNN. This ensures the accurate representation of the QRS complex within a fixed window of 292 spike steps.

Moreover, the SNN accelerator has been enriched to allow two distinct SNN models to be executed concurrently. Memory resources have been added to store two independent

Latency contributors	Samples	Time
Peak-detection offset (from true R-peak)	≈ 35	≈ 97 ms
Acquisition after detected peak	146	406 ms
Classifier inference	—	4.05 ms

TABLE II: Breakdown of latency contributors in the proposed pipeline, including peak detection offset, window completion, and classifier inference time.

Fig. 3: Architecture of the SNN processor.

sets of neuron potentials, representing the context of each SNN, and a *control module* was introduced, that permits a fast context switch between the two networks when a peak detection occurs. In particular, when the first SNN detects the peak, the control module enables heart beat classification by executing the second network, feeding the accelerator with the input of the segmentation buffer, selecting the correct set of weights to be fetched, and accessing neuron potentials from the corresponding context memory.

The peak detector in our system typically identifies the R-peak with a small intrinsic offset of about 35 samples, meaning the detected peak occurs approximately 35 samples (97 ms) after the true R-peak position. After a peak is detected, the system continues to acquire additional samples in order to assemble the required 292-sample, peak-centered window for classification. Since the detection offset is already included in this acquisition period, no extra delay is introduced by the offset itself. Once the peak is detected, the number of additional samples that must be acquired to complete the input window is 146, corresponding to 406 ms at a sampling rate of 360 Hz. This acquisition time constitutes the main contributor to the overall latency, while the actual classification step requires only 4.05 ms. Table II summarizes the main sources of latency in our processing pipeline.

The circular buffer that stores delta-encoded spikes for all six channels occupies $292 \times 6 = 1752$ bits (≈ 219 bytes), which fits comfortably into a single on-chip BRAM block. Both segmentation and buffering are implemented entirely in synchronous logic.

Finally, we created an adequate decoding slot that implements per-channel spike count and voting, which is used to obtain the classification results from both SNNs. The classification results are then transmitted through the UART interface as a system output.

The encoding and decoding functionalities are entirely mapped onto dedicated FPGA logic slots, which directly interact with the SNN accelerator. The RISC-V processor is limited to supervisory and I/O management tasks, ensuring

that the main pipeline (from delta encoding to arrhythmia classification) remains fully self-sufficient in hardware, with no dependency on external computation.

Syntzulu is designed for low-end FPGA deployment, such as the Lattice iCE40UP5K, ensuring efficiency and scalability in near-sensor AI applications. Table III reports the resource utilization of the revised version of the system presented in this work. Compared to the previous implementation, the updated design achieves a substantial reduction in logic cell (LC) usage (from 89% to 70.4%) and BRAM occupation (from 93% to 66.7%), while also lowering the number of DSP blocks from 3 to 2. These optimizations are made possible by integrating peak detection and classification within a unified SNN pipeline, avoiding redundant memory and computation stages.

LC	DSP	BRAM	SPRAM
3718 (70.4%)	2 (25 %)	20 (66.7 %)	4 (100 %)

TABLE III: Resource utilization of the proposed system on the Lattice iCE40UP5K FPGA.

V. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

This section contains the experimental findings pertaining to the evaluation of the suggested ECG monitoring system's performance in terms of classification accuracy and the effectiveness of on-hardware inference.

A. Encoding Assessment

We initiated our evaluation by assessing the efficacy of the proposed encoding approach. Our analysis encompassed three progressively complex scenarios, each incorporating an expanding set of signals for classification. Initially, we applied delta modulation solely to the raw signal. Subsequently, we introduced the first-order derivative into the process. Finally, we included the second-order derivative to explore its additional benefits. To systematically evaluate the impact of these encoding strategies, we conducted three distinct training trials, progressively incorporating up to six traces of spikes as input to the SNN.

Beyond the raw ECG, derivative-based encodings enrich the feature space available to the classifier. The first derivative emphasizes slope dynamics, while the second derivative highlights curvature variations. This additional information translates into measurable performance gains: accuracy improves by +0.6% when the first derivative is included, and by an additional +0.16% when the second derivative is added, resulting in a total improvement of +0.76% compared to the raw-only baseline.

These results highlight the benefits of using the raw signal along with its derivatives. Through delta modulation, we converted these signals into spike-based representations, improving their informativeness for SNNs and enhancing classification performance. As shown in Figure 2, each derived trace captures different aspects of the raw signal's dynamics.

Patient	TP	FP	FN	Patient	TP	FP	FN
100	347	0	0	101	272	0	0
103	305	0	0	105	386	9	8
106	294	2	11	108	147	12	141
109	371	2	2	111	330	0	0
112	374	0	0	113	279	14	0
114	321	0	1	115	291	0	0
116	374	0	1	117	233	0	0
118	350	18	15	119	297	1	0
121	323	10	10	122	373	0	0
123	229	0	0	124	264	0	0
200	354	0	7	201	363	0	3
202	429	0	1	203	403	1	25
205	369	0	0	207	187	57	35
208	412	1	1	209	437	1	2
210	392	0	3	212	395	0	0
213	478	0	0	214	345	0	0
215	498	1	0	219	334	2	2
220	311	0	0	221	346	1	2
222	427	0	12	223	389	0	0
228	308	11	5	230	369	3	2
231	279	0	0	232	267	5	2
233	456	1	1	234	405	0	0

TABLE IV: True positives, false positives, and false negatives of our peak detection with a tolerance of 50 samples for each ECG recording on the MIT-BIH arrhythmia database.

The multi-layer encoding approach thus provides a richer representation of physiological patterns. Based on these findings, we selected the six-input model as the optimal configuration for further evaluations.

B. Peak detection performance

To refine the detection process, a filtering mechanism was introduced on the processed output to reduce redundant close-range detections and suppress irrelevant events. Specifically, within each detected event region, only the first occurrence was retained if multiple detections fell within a predefined temporal window, preventing excessive activations caused by minor fluctuations in spike activity. Figure 4 illustrates the complete process, from the initial spike output to the final identification of peak events. To ensure a physiologically consistent separation between detected beats, we applied a two-step event filtering mechanism. First, a temporal filtering window of 120 samples (approximately one-third of a second) was used to retain only the first occurrence of multiple detections within the same region. Second, we eliminated irrelevant peak events by discarding those associated with dominance regions smaller than 20 samples. This combined approach enhances detection reliability by maintaining a balance between sensitivity and specificity in peak identification.

The results reported in Table IV demonstrate the high accuracy of our peak detection algorithm when evaluated on the MIT-BIH Arrhythmia Database. Specifically, the model was trained using an 8-bit quantization-aware approach, effectively reducing the precision of network weights while maintaining robust performance. Overall, the analysis shows robust outcomes, achieving a PPV of 0.990 and a TPR of 0.981, considering a detection valid if located within a 50-sample tolerance window around the ground truth label.

Fig. 4: Visualization of different stages of the peak detection process for patient 213 from top to bottom. (a) Spike output of the network in response to the input ECG signal. (b) Identified dominant class regions based on spike rate evaluation. (c) Peak events results from identification of dominant regions. (d) Final detected events after applying filtering mechanisms.

The analysis highlights distinct signal quality issues across different patients. Patient 108, for instance, presents significant baseline fluctuations and high noise levels, which compromise peak detection accuracy. These conditions result in a PPV of 0.924 and a TPR of 0.510, both below the overall average, suggesting that the algorithm struggles with peak identification due to baseline instability and excessive noise. Figure 5 visually illustrates these irregularities.

Similarly, patient 207's recording is affected by signal loss and interference, leading to sporadic missing segments and waveform distortions that degrade detection performance. The computed PPV and TPR for this case are 0.766 and 0.842, respectively. The lower PPV indicates an increase in false positives, likely due to misclassified interference, while the TPR suggests that some peaks are still detected despite the signal gaps. Figure 6 depicts these disruptions, highlighting interruptions and unwanted artifacts.

The performance metrics of the peak detection algorithm are highly encouraging. The PPV statistics (Min: 0.766, Q1: 0.994, Median: 1.000, Q3: 1.000) indicate that, on average, the algorithm achieves near-perfect precision across the dataset. Similarly, the TPR statistics (Min: 0.510, Q1: 0.992, Median: 0.998, Q3: 1.000) demonstrate an equally high sensitivity, with most recordings exhibiting optimal performance. Figure 7

Fig. 5: Example signal from patient 108, showing significant baseline fluctuations and noise.

Fig. 6: Example signal from patient 207, showing loss of signal and interference effects.

displays the boxplot of PPV and TPR per patient, which visually confirms the narrow interquartile ranges and the overall high medians. The few lower bound values suggest the presence of a limited number of challenging cases (likely affected by noise or artifacts) that require further investigation

Fig. 7: Boxplot illustrating the variability of ECG peak detection metrics PPV and TPR across individual patients. Median values are explicitly annotated.

and possible algorithmic refinement.

Notably, excluding patient 108, the overall metrics significantly improve to PPV = 0.991 and TPR = 0.990; further excluding patient 207 leads to an even higher performance, with PPV = 0.994 and TPR = 0.992.

C. Classification performance

To optimize memory usage and enhance efficiency on the chosen hardware platform, the model underwent quantization, limiting the precision of neuronal parameters to 8 bits, achieving a four-fold reduction in model size. This compression led to a negligible decrease in accuracy, with the largest observed drop being only 0.1%. The quantized model achieves 98.4% accuracy, with 88.11% sensitivity, 97.66% specificity, and an F1-score of 88.6 on the test set. The window-shift augmentation resulted in a relative increase of +3.8% in sensitivity and +1.2% in specificity. For completeness, Table V reports the confusion matrix obtained with the model trained without augmentation, while Table VI presents the final confusion matrix when data augmentation is exploited during training. As can be observed, the results in Table V show a significant amount of false negatives, especially S and V beats mistakenly classified as N. The effect of augmentation in training is an improved sensitivity for the minority classes, resulting in F1 score values of 99.19% for the N class, 80.42% for the S class, and 95.76% for the V class, obtained from the numbers in Table VI.

In all reported evaluations, performance metrics were computed exclusively on the main arrhythmia classes (N, S, V, and F), consistently excluding the Q category. This choice was motivated both by the negligible prevalence of class Q samples in the dataset and to facilitate a fair comparison with prior works that predominantly report results on the four-class problem.

The classification performance of the model was further assessed under noisy test conditions, demonstrating an accuracy drop up to 86.37% on the dataset collecting ECG signals at SNR levels of 3 dB, 10 dB, and 24 dB. To address this issue, we repeated the training of the model including noisy samples. This new assessment shows that competitive performance is maintained across all test scenarios (96.33% accuracy at SNR

TABLE V: Confusion matrix illustrating the classification performance of the 8-bit quantized model on the test set before augmentation.

True Labels	N	S	V	F	Q
	N	17960	15	19	2
S	124	345	4	0	0
V	80	1	1014	2	0
F	32	0	8	109	0
Q	3	0	1	0	0
	N	S	V	F	Q

TABLE VI: Confusion matrix illustrating the classification performance of the 8-bit quantized model on the test set after augmentation.

True Labels	N	S	V	F	Q
	N	17851	91	34	20
S	82	386	5	0	0
V	35	7	1051	4	0
F	26	3	7	113	0
Q	3	0	1	0	0
	N	S	V	F	Q

levels of 3 dB, 10 dB, and 24 dB; 96.76% at SNR levels of 10 dB and 24 dB; and 96.98% at 24 dB), despite a small drop in noiseless accuracy to 97.01%.

Finally, to extend the evaluation of the proposed approach to a larger amount of data, we trained the same topology on a different dataset, the MIT-BIH Atrial Fibrillation Database. The dataset was partitioned following the same protocol adopted for the peak classification task, with 70% of the data used for training, 10% for validation, and 20% for testing. The assessment demonstrated a 91.5% accuracy, 84.45% sensitivity, 89.92% precision, 94.42% specificity, and 86.87% F1-score. The lower performance compared to MIT-BIH Arrhythmia (98.4% accuracy) can be explained by the more balanced class distribution and the reduced sampling frequency of the dataset. To the best of our knowledge, no other SNN-based studies have reported results on this dataset, preventing direct comparison with related works.

D. Sparsity

SNNs inherently apply sparsity, as only a limited number of neurons are active at any given time. To measure this effect, we evaluated the overall sparsity across the network layers using Equation 5.

$$Sparsity = \left(1 - \frac{\sum_{i=1}^L \sum_{j=1}^{N_i} n_{ij}}{\sum_{i=1}^L N_i} \right) \times 100 \quad (5)$$

Where:

- L is the total number of layers in the network,
- N_i is the number of output neurons in the i -th layer,
- n_{ij} indicates whether the j -th neuron in the i -th layer is active (1 if active, 0 otherwise).

This equation determines the percentage of inactive spikes relative to the maximum possible spike count in the network. For the peak detection module, the computed sparsity

Fig. 8: The sparsity distributions for neurons in layers 1 to 4 (from top to bottom) of the peak detection model are shown. The semi-transparent vertical line marks the threshold beyond which neurons exhibit zero activity.

Fig. 9: The sparsity distributions for neurons in layers 1 to 4 (from top to bottom) of the arrhythmia classification model are shown. The semi-transparent vertical line marks the threshold beyond which neurons exhibit zero activity.

reached 83%, meaning that, on average, only 17% of potential spikes were active. Figure 8 illustrates the spike distribution across layers for the peak detection model. In the arrhythmia classification module, sparsity was slightly lower, reaching 92%, indicating an average of 8% active spikes. Figure 9 details how the network architecture influences sparsity in the classification model, with values averaged over the test set.

Although the measured sparsity provides insight into the computational sparsity of SNNs, the parallelism enforced by the neuron cores represents a limitation in the efficiency of sparsity exploitation. In detail, as the spikes are processed in groups of four, only groups of four consecutive inactive

synapses can be skipped and are directly translated into inference time savings. To account for this inefficiency, we introduce a new metric, *sparsity-hw*, which is defined by Equation 6, i.e., introducing in Equation 5 the concept of a group representing 4 consecutive synapses.

$$Sparsity-hw = \left(1 - \frac{\sum_{i=1}^L \sum_{j=1}^{G_i} g_{ij}}{\sum_{i=1}^L G_i} \right) \times 100 \quad (6)$$

Where:

- G_i is the number of spike groups in the i -th layer,
- g_{ij} indicates whether there's at least one active spike in the j -th group in the i -th layer.

By enforcing the organization of synapses into groups during software inference execution, we assessed a *sparsity-hw* value of 61% for the peak detection model, and of 85% for the classification model, representing the actual percentage of computation savings that can be exploited on Syntzulu on average.

The proposed design leverages the intrinsic sparsity of spiking activity, ensuring that neurons are activated only when required by significant signal events. This translates into dynamic power minimization during idle periods, while still allocating full resources when needed to preserve accuracy. This mechanism differs from pruning or model compression techniques, as no permanent reduction of computation is enforced, thus guaranteeing that classification accuracy is not compromised.

E. Power consumption

To evaluate the energy efficiency of the FPGA implementation, we analyzed the execution time of the selected SNN model, considering the impact of varying sparsity. While direct hardware measurements of power consumption were carried out, an analytical approach was additionally adopted to estimate the average execution time across the test set. This was necessary since execution time and, consequently, energy usage are strongly beat-dependent and cannot be universally derived from physical measurements alone. It is important to clarify that the term *energy per inference* refers specifically to the peak detection module, as this model continuously processes incoming ECG samples, performing one inference per input sample. Conversely, we use the term *energy per classification* to denote the arrhythmia classification module, as its computation involves analyzing an entire window of samples each time a peak is detected.

To determine the number of cycles required for a single arrhythmia classification, we first analyze the computational load imposed by the selected network topology, which amounts to 5,083,136 *ops*. We then introduced two scaling factors to reflect hardware-level parallelism: the integration of two pipelined neuron modules and the simultaneous processing of four spikes. Finally, we incorporated the efficiency gains provided by *sparsity-hw*. Taking into account the parallel processing capabilities of the reference accelerator, we derived an expected execution time of approximately 97,205 cycles for the arrhythmia classification module, as defined by Equation 7.

TABLE VII: Comparative summary of representative works on ECG classification using spiking neural networks. ASIC- and FPGA-based results are reported separately, and for the FPGA category we highlight the best-performing event-driven ECG implementations identified in the literature, which serve as the basis for our direct comparison.

Work	Dataset	Encoding	Cls.	Acc (%)	Sen (%)	Spe (%)	F ₁	Device	Energy	Power
H. Chu et al. [14]	MIT-BIH	LC-ADC	5	98.22	—	—	—	ASIC	0.75 μ J	0.93 μ W
H. Chu et al. [19]	MIT-BIH	LC-ADC	—	98.24	—	—	—	ASIC	0.36 μ J	1.35 μ W
Y. Liu et al. [21]	MIT-BIH	LC-ADC	4	90.5	—	—	—	ASIC	0.53 pJ/spk	0.35 μ W
H. Fan et al. [16]	MIT-BIH	Dual-Bin	5	96.8	—	—	—	ASIC	0.16 μ J	12.19 μ W
R. Mao et al. [15]	MIT-BIH	Dual-Bin	5	98.6	—	—	—	ASIC	0.30 μ J	—
J. Loh et al. [22]	MIT-BIH	Temporal	2	94.0	—	—	79	ASIC	—	2.2 μ W
Z. Yan et al. [20]	MIT-BIH	Rate	4	98.29	88.97*	98.19*	89.41*	ASIC	0.031 μ J	6.1 μ W
Y. Xing et al. [27]	MIT-BIH	Binary	5	98.26	84.69*	96.99*	89.44*	FPGA	346.33 μ J	250 mW
A. Rana et al. [28]	PTB-ECG	Poisson	2	85.0	—	—	—	FPGA	—	176 mW
Our work	MIT-BIH	Delta mod.	5	98.4	88.11	97.66	88.6	FPGA	36.86 μJ	9.1 mW

* values recalculated from the confusion matrix provided.

Similarly, the peak detection network requires approximately 1,044 cycles for each inference.

$$execution\ cycles = \frac{ops \cdot (1 - sparsity \cdot hw)}{modules \cdot parallel\ spikes} \quad (7)$$

Considering a system clock frequency of 24 MHz, we derived an execution time of 4.05 ms for the arrhythmia classification model. Additionally, the peak detection model requires approximately 0.04 ms for a single inference.

For power analysis, we utilized a Digilent Analog Discovery 2 oscilloscope along with three $1.0 \pm 0.01 \Omega$ shunt resistors, connected to the three distinct power inputs of the Lattice iCE40UP5k FPGA: Vcore, VCCIO0&1, and VCCIO2. The Vcore line supplies 1 V to the FPGA's internal components, whereas VCCIO0&1 and VCCIO2 provide 3.3 V to the I/O pins. During classification, data acquisition, and processing, we measured an average power consumption of 9.1 mW. Given the previously computed execution times, the energy required for a single arrhythmia classification amounts to 36.86 μ J, while the peak detection inference consumes approximately 0.4 μ J.

As a practical example, consider a use case involving a patient with a heart rate of 120 beats per minute (bpm). In this scenario, the peak detection network runs continuously, processing each incoming ECG sample at the fixed sampling rate. Conversely, the arrhythmia classification network is triggered only upon detection of a heartbeat, resulting in 120 inferences per minute if all beats are correctly identified. Considering the energy consumption of both networks and focusing solely on the inference tasks, the resulting average power consumption amounts to approximately 0.45 mW.

F. Discussion

This section discusses the proposed system in relation to both prior literature and complementary evaluation scenarios. We first analyze how our approach compares with state-of-the-art SNN-based ECG classifiers, focusing on accuracy, energy efficiency, and hardware scalability. Subsequently, we extend the analysis to alternative evaluation protocols and datasets, highlighting the challenges and opportunities that arise when assessing robustness in more realistic conditions.

1) Comparative Analysis: Table VII lists the main contributions, designs, and performance metrics of the foundational studies addressing ECG arrhythmia classification with SNN-based solutions. As can be observed, the proposed ECG monitoring system achieves a classification accuracy comparable to the best-performing SNN models in the literature, exceeding the 98.28% and 98.26% accuracy reported by [20] and [27], and representing the best alternative to [15], which achieves an impressive 98.6% accuracy on the MIT-BIH dataset.

The importance of energy consumption is underscored by previous works as well. For example, [16] reports 0.16 μ J per classification, whereas [15] achieves 0.3 μ J, outperforming the energy efficiency of our FPGA-based solution. Our FPGA-based solution exhibits a higher energy cost per inference than these ASIC implementations. However, the reconfigurable nature of our design offers greater versatility in terms of prototyping and real-time adaptability.

On the contrary, our implementation significantly outperforms the power efficiency of both considered FPGA alternatives. In [27], an SNN with an integrated attention mechanism achieves a notable 98.26% accuracy on the MIT-BIH dataset, with an energy consumption of 346 μ J on the Artix-7 FPGA. Similarly, [28] introduces a binarized SNN demonstrating 85% accuracy in distinguishing normal from abnormal beats in the PTB Diagnostic ECG Database. Despite targeting a different classification task, it provides a valuable reference point for FPGA-based power metrics, demonstrating an average power consumption of 176 mW. To the best of our knowledge, [27] and [28] represent the most relevant alternatives for neuromorphic ECG classification on FPGA. Although [28] and [27] do not disclose detailed post-synthesis figures, both target much larger FPGAs: an Artix-7 XC7A100T (≈ 63 k LUTs) and a Zynq-7000 XC7Z020 (≈ 53 k LUTs), respectively. By contrast, our complete ECG SNN fits on the iCE40-UP5K, using only 3522 LUTs—about 70 % of the 5k available—thus demonstrating comparable functionality on a device that offers over an order of magnitude fewer logic resources.

The efficiency of our system is primarily attributed to the spike-based encoding, which ensures high sparsity and significantly reduces computational overhead. Moreover, integrating a peak detection mechanism that leverages these same encoding modules further enhances efficiency. Unlike more conventional methods requiring additional filtering blocks, our

approach capitalizes on structured spike representations to locate peak positions with minimal overhead, thereby reducing resource utilization.

These advantages, combined with the optimized hardware architecture, result in the lowest energy footprint among FPGA-based solutions [27], [28], making our system particularly suitable for continuous ECG monitoring in scenarios requiring standalone, real-time analysis.

2) *Extended Evaluation*: To complement the baseline intra-patient results, we extended the evaluation to alternative protocols and datasets, including inter-patient generalization, noise robustness, and atrial fibrillation recordings. These tests provide a broader view of the system’s applicability in real-world scenarios, where variability and artifacts are unavoidable, while also introducing specific challenges that will be discussed in the following sections.

To rigorously assess the generalization capability of the proposed system to previously unseen patients, we performed an inter-patient evaluation on the MIT-BIH Arrhythmia Database following the standard *Chazal* partitioning protocol [4]. To address the well-known limitations of morphology-only inter-patient training, the original SNN architecture was extended with a rhythm-informed late-fusion branch, and training was augmented with an RR-regularized loss term designed to penalize physiologically implausible predictions.

Specifically, the ECG-based classifier is extended with an additional lightweight layer implementing a dedicated RR branch, which bypasses the feature extractor and injects rhythm information only at the output stage. Pre- and post-beat RR intervals are encoded using a spike-rate representation and combined with ECG-derived features at the late-fusion stage. In this way, rhythm information acts as a corrective signal while preserving morphology-driven discrimination.

Under this revised setting, inter-patient sensitivity improves substantially from 43.45% to 60.48% (+17.3 pp), while overall accuracy increases from 92.44% to 92.78%. The macro-averaged F1-score rises from 0.425 to 0.561, indicating a more balanced behavior across arrhythmia classes. The most pronounced gain is observed for supraventricular ectopic beats, whose sensitivity improves from 0.22% to 64.06%, confirming that rhythm cues effectively mitigate patient-specific morphological bias.

A patient-wise error analysis further clarifies the origin of the remaining performance gap. While a limited number of subjects exhibit accuracies in the 70–85% range, the majority of patients achieve stable and high performance: 58% exceed 95% accuracy and 33% exceed 99%. This distribution indicates that the degradation in aggregate inter-patient metrics is driven by a small subset of challenging cases rather than by a uniform failure across subjects.

Fusion beats remain the most problematic category under strict inter-patient conditions due to their extreme sparsity and intrinsic ambiguity. Excluding the fusion class has only a marginal effect on overall accuracy (92.78% to 93.53%), but leads to a pronounced improvement in averaged sensitivity (60.48% to 80.63%) and F1-score (0.561 to 0.756), indicating that fusion-related errors disproportionately dominate multi-class indicators.

When the task is reformulated as binary anomaly detection by merging all abnormal beats into a single class, the rhythm-informed model achieves 94.22% accuracy, with 83.28% sensitivity, 95.57% specificity, and an F1-score of 0.7597 under the same strict inter-patient split. This result highlights that, although fine-grained arrhythmia discrimination across unseen patients remains challenging, the proposed architecture provides robust patient-independent abnormality detection, consistent with typical clinical screening requirements.

Despite these improvements, strict inter-patient evaluation still leads to a marked degradation in both sensitivity and specificity, in line with prior SNN-based studies adopting the same protocol. For instance, [14] reports 93.7% accuracy with 55.5% specificity, while Yan *et al.* [17] achieve 90% accuracy with 61.5% sensitivity and 76% specificity. Higher figures are generally reported only when relaxing the evaluation protocol through patient-specific fine-tuning [16], confirming that the remaining performance gap is largely intrinsic to strict inter-patient ECG classification rather than specific to the proposed architecture.

We further investigated the robustness of the system to noise artifacts by corrupting MIT-BIH signals with controlled levels of electrode motion noise, using the MIT-BIH Noise Stress Test Database. Results confirm that the baseline model (trained on noiseless data) achieves the highest accuracy in clean conditions but suffers a marked performance drop under noise (86.37% at SNR levels of 3 dB, 10 dB, and 24 dB). In contrast, the noise-trained model preserves competitive accuracy across all scenarios (96.33% at SNR levels of 3 dB, 10 dB, and 24 dB; 96.76% at SNR levels of 10 dB and 24 dB; and 96.98% at 24 dB). A consistent trend was observed in peak detection: while the baseline detector degraded under noise (PPV = 0.947, TPR = 0.960), the noise-trained version maintained more stable values (PPV = 0.970, TPR = 0.970), confirming that noise-aware training benefits both heartbeat classification and detection.

Finally, to assess applicability to different clinical contexts, we evaluated the model on the MIT-BIH Atrial Fibrillation Database. The achieved performance was 91.5% accuracy, with sensitivity 0.8445, precision 0.8992, specificity 0.9442, and F1-score 0.8687. The lower performance compared to MIT-BIH Arrhythmia (98.4% accuracy) can be attributed to the more balanced class distribution and reduced sampling frequency of this dataset. To the best of our knowledge, no prior SNN-based studies have reported results on this benchmark, preventing direct comparison.

Overall, these findings underscore that robust generalization across unseen patients remains an unsolved challenge for ultra-low-power SNN-based ECG classifiers. Patient-specific fine-tuning, as also observed in our case (accuracy on a representative subject, patient 213, increasing from 82.62% to 94.44%), partially mitigates these limitations, while noise training enhances resilience to artifacts. Looking ahead, achieving reliable inter-patient performance will likely require adaptive or domain-adaptation strategies, together with broader evaluations across diverse datasets and acquisition conditions.

VI. CONCLUSION

This work presents a low-power ECG monitoring system for real-time arrhythmia detection, integrating Spiking Neural Networks (SNNs) with an optimized event-driven peak detection mechanism and delta modulation-based encoding. A key innovation of this study is the elimination of traditional peak detection algorithms, replacing them with an SNN-based QRS detection module, which achieves a Positive Predictive Value of 99% and a True Positive Rate of 98.1%. This integration reduces computational redundancy and enhances processing efficiency.

The proposed spike encoding scheme, which incorporates both first- and second-order derivatives, improves feature extraction and increases data sparsity. This results in a 0.76% accuracy gain over baseline methods, contributing to the final classification accuracy of 98.4% on the MIT-BIH dataset, aligning with state-of-the-art SNN solutions.

Another major contribution of this work is the fully integrated FPGA-based hardware architecture, optimized for real-time SNN processing while minimizing power consumption. By merging peak detection and classification into a unified pipeline, the system achieves an inference time of 4.05 ms per classification with an energy consumption of 36.86, significantly outperforming existing FPGA-based alternatives.

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Matteo Antonio Scrugli received his bachelor's degree with honors in 2018 from the University of Cagliari and his Ph.D. in 2022 in electrical engineering from the University of Cagliari at the DIEE department. His research mainly concerns the development of systems capable of managing at runtime the hardware and software configuration of low-power devices in order to adapt it to the required operating mode. Recent work has focused on cognitive IoT devices, particularly those implementing neuromorphic models and processing bio-signals. These devices are designed to operate on single-core or multi-core platforms, as well as FPGAs, enabling efficient edge-computing capabilities.

Gianluca Leone has been an assistant professor at the University of Cagliari, Italy, since 2023. He earned his Ph.D. in Electronics and Computer Engineering from the University of Cagliari in 2023. He received his M.S. degree in Electronics Engineering from the Politecnico di Torino, Italy, in 2019, and his B.S. degree in Electronics Engineering from the University of Cagliari in 2016. His research focuses on the design and optimization of digital systems. His recent work includes the development of FPGA-based systems for processing biosignals and SNN-type workloads in real-time at the edge. He teaches Integrated Systems Design and Mixed-Signal Circuits and Systems at the University of Cagliari.

Paola Busia received the Ph.D. degree in Electronics and Computer Engineering from Università degli studi di Cagliari, Italy, in 2023. She is currently assistant professor at Università degli studi di Cagliari. Her main research interests involve power efficient processing architectures for embedded applications and for at-the-edge AI.

Luigi Raffo received the Laurea Degree in electronic engineering and the Ph.D. degree in electronics and computer science from the University of Genoa, Italy, in 1989 and 1994, respectively. In 1994, he joined the Department of Electrical and Electronic Engineering, University of Cagliari, Italy, as an Assistant Professor and as an Associate Professor, in 1998. He has been a Full Professor of electronics with the Department of Electrical and Electronic Engineering, University of Cagliari, Italy, since 2006. He teaches courses on system/digital and analog electronic design and processor architectures for the Courses of studies in electronic and biomedical engineering. He was a Coordinator of the project EU IST-FET - IST-2001-39266 - BEST and the MADNESS EU Project (FP7/2007-2013). He was also a Unit Coordinator of the project EU IST-FET - SHAPES - Scalable Software Hardware Architecture Platform for Embedded Systems. He is also a Local Coordinator of industrial projects in the field (among others: ST-Microelectronics - Extension of ST200 architecture for ARM binary compatibility and ST-Microelectronics - Network on chip). He is responsible for the cooperation programs in the field of embedded systems with several other European Universities. He was a Local Coordinator of the ASAM (ARTEMIS-JU) and ALBA projects (national founded project) and RPCT (regional founded project).

Paolo Meloni is an associate professor at the University of Cagliari. His research activity is on the development of advanced digital systems, on the application-driven design and programming of multi-core on-chip architectures and FPGAs. He is the author of a significant track of international research papers. He teaches Microcontroller-based systems and Advanced embedded systems at Università degli studi di Cagliari.